

Effect of Nanoclay Loading on Mechanical Properties of Nanocomposites

Azmi Nordin, Ren Baosheng, Junji NODA, Koichi GODA
Department of Mechanical Engineering, Yamaguchi University,
Tokiwadai, Ube, Yamaguchi, 755-8611
m029ve@yamaguchi-u.ac.jp

SUMMARY

In this study, to investigate the relation between the agglomerates and mechanical properties, their dispersion state and size distribution were analyzed, using an electron probe micro analyzer (EPMA). Finally the micro-structure of the nanocomposites was discussed from the standpoint of nanoclay clustering intensity.

Keywords: Nanocomposites, Nanoclay, Epoxy resin, Tensile strength, EPMA

1. Introduction

Composite materials have demonstrated weight savings for aircraft structures, outstanding corrosion resistance and fatigue-damage tolerance. Accordingly, composite materials have been extensively applied to the areas of aerospace, aircraft, sports and military industries. However, the improvements in composites properties have never reached to the end [1-4]. Composite materials are often reinforced by stiff fillers. The efficiency of reinforcement depends on the filler aspect ratio, the filler mechanical properties and the adhesion between the matrix and the filler. In order to deal with the limitation in stiffness and strength of polymers, inorganic particulate fillers such as carbon nanotubes, layered silicate and so on, are often added to polymer composites. Particulate fillers then modify the physical and mechanical properties of polymers. Moreover, these properties depend on particle size, particle/matrix interface adhesion and particle loading [5].

The polymer-layered silicate nanocomposites have been widely investigated in literature over the past few years for their high potential [3-4, 10-13]. It has been broadly reported that single clay layers are proposed as an ideal reinforcing agents due to their extremely high aspect ratio and also the thickness of the nanometer filler is comparable to the scale of the polymer chain structure [6-7]. Montmorillonite is the most commonly used layered

silicate and its structure consists of around 1nm thickness and the lateral dimensions of these layers may vary from 30nm to several microns or larger. In addition, it is believed that the complete exfoliation of silicate layers in the polymer matrix can improve the properties of epoxy-clay nanocomposites [3]. However, to produce complete exfoliation of silicates layer needs precise processing techniques which have attracted a great intention in this field of study. To investigate the properties of polymer-clay nanocomposites is not yet finished at just as an experimental data; moreover, modeling the nanocomposites also has been reported as overall completion to the experimental procedure [6-9].

In the present study, the mechanical properties of epoxy-nanoclay nanocomposites were investigated and discussed structurally based on the different nanoclay loading amount. The compounding of nanoclay in an epoxy resin brings a structural change which revealed the presence of micro-structure of the nanoclay cluster inside the epoxy resin. In related, the structure of epoxy matrix filled with silicate clay particles have been investigated in order to find a visualized reason for the experimental results. Commonly, the structure of nanocomposites has typically been established using wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) analysis, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) or transmission electron micrographic (TEM) observation [14]. However, the structure regarding the size distribution and clustering of nanoclay particles/agglomerates has not been investigated quantitatively. In this study, therefore, we used the electron probe micro-analyzer (EPMA) to analyze the quantitative micro-structure of the nanocomposites and their micro-structure was discussed from the concept of nanoclay clustering intensity.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

In this study, Araldite AY103-1 and hardener, HY956 provided by HUNTSMAN Co., Ltd, were mixed in the weight ratio of 10:3 to perform thermoplastic resin. As for nanoclay, the Nanomer®I.28E nanoclay provided by Nanocor Inc., was used. This nanoclay is an onium ion surface modified montmorillonite mineral. Montmorillonite mineral is classified as the magnesium aluminum silicate, which can be used to make a new class of clay-polymer. A few weight percent of layered silicates that are properly dispersed throughout the polymer matrix thus create much higher surface area for polymer/filler interaction as compared to conventional composites [14].

2.2 Specimen preparation

2.2.1 Nanoclay loading methodology

From the previous studies, it is recommended to use small amount of nanoclay, typically in the range of 3-5wt% for improvements in mechanical properties of nanocomposites [15, 16]. In this study, 1phr, 2phr and 3phr of nanoclay was used. Both resin and nanoclay were measured in weight and mixed in a beaker by using the sonication device, Branson Sonifier 450, for about 10 minutes [11]. While mixing, the beaker was placed in cold water to avoid the increase in the solution's temperature during the sonication process [2]. For this reason, the solution's temperature was measured by using a thermometer for every minute and the cold water which was used for external cooling was changed every two minutes. Then, the hardener was added to the solution and stirred for about two more minutes.

2.2.2 Neat epoxy resin and nanoclay loading resin plate specimens

In this study, a new metallic mold for making the specimens was designed. The mold contains five slots with a depth of 0.6mm and width of 5.0mm at the central part to form a fixed shape for the plate specimens. Mold lubricant, produced by HUNTSMAN Co., Ltd., was beforehand applied to avoid the epoxy resin adhere to the metallic mold. The epoxy resin or nanoclay loading epoxy resin was poured into the slot on the metallic mold. The mold was then placed in a vacuum pump for 10 minutes to remove air bubbles from the resin. The specimens were cured completely after placing them in a Homoisothermal drier (SANYO Corp., MOV-112F) for 24 hours at 30°C, and then for 6.5 hours at 60°C.

2.3 Measurements

2.3.1 Tensile test

In order to investigate the influence of nanoclay loading on the mechanical properties of the specimens, a tensile test was done. In this study, we used an INSTRON type testing machine (Autograph IS5000 by Shimadzu Corp., load capacity of 49.03kN), meanwhile a strain amplifier (Kyowa Electronic Instruments Co., Ltd., DPM-700B) and a strain gauge (Kyowa Electronic Instrument Co., Ltd., KGF-5-120-C1-11L1M2R) were used for strain measurement. A memory recorder (GRAPHTEC Corp., WR85000) was used for recording the load and strain. The thickness and width for each specimen were measured respectively at three points; the both ends of a gauge part and the central part of the specimens before the aluminum tab were adhering to the both ends of the specimens. Those average values were recognized as the specimen size. The tensile test was carried out until the specimen fractured at the crosshead speed of 1mm/min under the room temperature.

2.3.2 EPMA observation

In order to investigate the distribution and size of nanoclay agglomerates, two parts from the tested specimens, fracture surface and cross-section, were observed through the electron probe micro-analyzer (Shimadzu Corp., hereinafter denoted as EPMA). For fracture surface observation, each of the fractured specimens was cut into pieces from the fracture surface. Meanwhile, the samples for fracture surface observation were cut into 2mm pieces from the fracture surface to observe the cross-sectional surface of each sample. Since resin itself is an insulator, the golden vapor deposition was carried out for each sample using micro ion weld slag equipment. After this procedure, those samples were observed.

3. Results and Discussions

The conventional epoxy resin specimen and the nanoclay loading epoxy resin plate specimen are hereinafter abbreviated as Neat and NE keywords. That is, nanoclay epoxy resin plate specimens by loading amount of 1phr, 2phr and 3phr are described as NE1, NE2 and NE3 respectively. The fracture and cross-sectional surface samples are described by adding 'F' and 'C' characters respectively.

3.1 Mechanical properties of Neat and nanoclay loading resin plate specimens

From the tensile test, strain-stress curves for Neat and NE1, NE2 and NE3 specimens were obtained and the mechanical properties of each specimen were compared. Figure 1 shows the representative stress-strain curves for each type of specimen. The results show that any curve appears with a relatively linear behavior and especially NE1, NE2 and NE3 specimens exhibit brittle behavior compared to Neat specimen. It is considered that nanoclay particles are agglomerated and their breaks bring premature fracture of the nanocomposites. On the other hand, by loading 1phr of nanoclay amount, NE1 curve shows higher stiffness compared to Neat specimen. The NE2 and NE3 curves, meanwhile, indicated the decrease in strength and stiffness.

Fig.1 Stress-strain curves for Neat and NE1, 2 and 3 specimens

Table 1 Mechanical properties of Neat and NE1, 2, and 3 specimens

	Number of specimens	Tensile strength [MPa]	Fracture strain [%]	Young's modulus [GPa]
Neat	2	40.4	2.85	1.85
NE1	5	40.1	2.19	2.54
NE2	5	34.5	2.67	1.70
NE3	5	30.7	2.18	1.59

Table 1 shows the average value of the mechanical properties for Neat, NE1, NE2 and NE3 specimens. From this table, we know that the Young's modulus of resin plate specimen increases up to 37% by loading 1phr of nanoclay amount. Moreover, by the same amount of nanoclay loading, the fracture strain decreases to 23%. On the other hand, the Young's modulus of NE2 and NE3 specimens decrease by 8% and 14% respectively compared to Neat specimens. According to the Ke Wang et al [4], nanoclay/epoxy composites decrease in strength with increasing of nanoclay loading without any optimum loading. In this study, however, we found an optimum nanoclay amount loading to keep the tensile strength and increase the Young's modulus.

3.2 Distribution of nanoclay by EPMA observation

The distribution of 1phr and 3phr nanoclay amount at the fracture surface and cross-sectional surface of each specimen were examined by using EPMA. The observation area for each sample is $500\mu\text{m} \times 500\mu\text{m}$. As for the condition of observation, sample current, acceleration voltage and beam size were given as $0.1\mu\text{m}$, 15kV and $1\mu\text{m}$ respectively. The

typical observation results on the Si element for NE1-F, NE1-C, NE3-F and NE3-C samples, i.e. fracture surface and cross-section surface of 1phr and 3phr samples, are shown in figures 2(a)-(d). From the other observation results, Mg and Al elements were detected at the same place as the Si element and we recognized these as nanoclay's agglomerates. In the EPMA analysis results, the element areas equal to $1\mu\text{m}^2$, which is the limit of EPMA resolution, were often detected. These are considered to be the smallest scale of the agglomerates or nanoclay particles of which the area is less than $1\mu\text{m}^2$. As observed in the figures 2(a)-(d), we can see that the maximum size of nanoclay's agglomerates were in the range of 25 to $35\mu\text{m}$. Furthermore, more agglomerates were detected at the fracture area and NE3 specimen's sample compared to the cross section surface area and NE1 sample.

Fig.2 Observation on Si element for (a) NE1-F (b) NE1-C (c) NE3-F and (d) NE3-C.

Table 2 The average value of image processing analysis results for each type specimen.

Samples	Number of samples	Total value of agglomerates area [μm^2]	Average size of agglomerates area [μm^2]	Maximum of agglomerates area [μm^2]	Agglomerates area ratio [%]	Number of agglomerates
NE1-F	3	9337	47	1188	3.73	205
NE1-C	3	4140	35	662	1.67	130
NE3-F	3	15662	34	1357	6.27	463
NE3-C	3	13245	26	1087	5.27	513

Table 2 shows the average value of the image processing analysis results for each type of specimen. From this table, the maximum of agglomerates area and the agglomerates area ratio show larger values at the fracture surface compared to the cross section surface for each type specimen, while the number of agglomerates shows a larger value in NE3-C sample as compared to NE3-F sample. The above results mean that the composites' fracture occurs at a cross-section on which larger agglomerates are more contained. On the other hand, their fracture is not necessarily determined by the number of agglomerates.

3.3 Proposed clustering evaluation method

In order to analyze quantitatively “larger and more agglomerates” found out in section 3.2, we attempt to take account of the concept of clustering as given below. First, the image result in $500 \times 500 \mu\text{m}^2$ area size was divided into a small area, $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$, to evaluate the size of the agglomerates and the tendency of clustering.

Fig.3 EPMA observation results: (a) larger number of small agglomerates area; (b) a few bigger agglomerates area.

Figure 3 shows an image result from EPMA observation while figure 3(a) shows a divided area, $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$, of full image result from EPMA observation which contains a larger number of small agglomerates compared to a few bigger agglomerates area as shown in figure 3(b). Next, we consider the meaning of agglomerates in each divided area. By comparing figures 3(a) and (b), even if the number of agglomerates is different, the total agglomerates size for both figures might be the same as $\sum S_i^a \approx \sum S_i^b$. However, we can find the difference in the value between both figures by comparing the averages of agglomerates size. Since the averages of agglomerates area in the figures can be evaluated as $S_i^b > S_i^a$, we interpret here that the larger average gives a stronger clustering characteristic. Thus, in order to indicate a clustering potential, we define the average of agglomerates size in each division as a clustering intensity. From the above theoretical background, we estimated statistical properties of clustering intensity for each sample through the Weibull distribution given as:

$$F(\bar{S}) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{\bar{S}}{S_0}\right)^m\right\} \quad (1)$$

Where, \bar{S} is the clustering intensity of each division m and S_0 are Weibull shape and scale parameters, respectively. Figure 4 shows a Weibull graph of NE1-F, NE1-C, NE3-F and NE3-C samples. In this Weibull graph, the mean rank method was used for estimation of the cumulative probabilities. The plotted NE1-C, NE1-F and NE-C samples show a bi-modal distribution, while NE3-F sample shows a uni-modal distribution. This is because the lower tail of the bi-modal distribution reveals non-agglomerates area or the agglomerates area which could not be detected due to being less than the beam size of $1.0 \mu\text{m}^2$. Thus, by taking account of the clustering intensity data more than $1.0 \mu\text{m}^2$, the estimates of Weibull parameters were determined through the least square method.

Fig.4 Weibull graph based on the agglomerates average value

Table 3 Estimated Weibull parameters for the distribution of clustering intensity more than $1 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Weibull parameters	NE1-F	NE1-C	NE3-F	NE3-C
m	0.474	0.242	1.01	0.652
$S_0 \mu\text{m}^2$	22.6	2.41	60.4	25.9

Table 3 shows the shape m and scale S_0 parameter estimates for each sample. From this table, the scale of clustering intensity is determined by S_0 and the shape parameter m means a clustering intensity variation. By comparing the values of S_0 , we noted that larger clustering intensity is respectively found at NE3 sample compared to NE1 sample, and at -F sample as compared to -C sample. Moreover, NE3-F sample has a less clustering intensity variation. By comparing such statistical properties of clustering intensity with the obtained

tensile strength, it may be interpreted that larger scale and less variation of clustering intensity bring less tensile strength. This is because the former means that the nanocomposite contains larger agglomerates, and the latter means that the larger agglomerates are contained more stably in it. The present evaluation may be one example of possible relations between clustering state and tensile strength. Verification by using more experimental and EPMA elemental data will be our future subject.

4. Conclusions

The nanocomposites consisting of an epoxy matrix filled with different amount of nanoclay were investigated. Mechanical properties of each specimen were examined by tensile test and the nanocomposites structure was observed through the EPMA analysis. The following conclusions can be highlighted from this study.

1. According to the experimental results, it is possible to improve the stiffness of epoxy resin based on the NE1 specimen's result. However, with 2phr or more nanoclay loading, it turned out that no improvement besides decrease the stiffness for each specimen. In other words, we find an optimum nanoclay amount to improve the properties of epoxy resin.
2. From the EPMA analysis results, we noted that the maximum sizes of nanoclay's agglomerates were in the range of 25 to 35 μ m. Furthermore, more and larger agglomerates were observed at the NE3 specimens compared to the NE1 specimens.
3. From the proposed clustering evaluation method, it was proved that larger scale and less variation of clustering intensity bring less strength of the nanocomposites.

Acknowledgements

The support of epoxy resin from the HUNTSMAN Co., Ltd. and nanoclay from Nanocor Inc. are hereby acknowledged. Authors also appreciate the guidance and information from Nanocor Inc. for using nanoclay. The authors are grateful to Mr. Morifuku from the Centre of Instrumental Analysis, Yamaguchi University for his encouragement and cooperation on guiding and assisting to use the EPMA machine.

References

- [1] Naveed A. Siddiqui, Ricky S.C. Woo, Jyang-Kyo Kim, Christopher C.K. Leung, Arshad Munir. Mode 1 interlaminar fracture behavior and mechanical properties of CFRP with nanoclay-filled epoxy matrix. *Compos Part A: Appl Sci Manuf* 2007;38:449-60
- [2] M.V. Hosur, A.A. Mohammed, S. Zainuddin, S.Jeelani. Processing of nanoclay filled sandwich composites and their response to low-velocity impact loading. *Compos Struct* 2008;82:101-16

- [3] Asma Yasmin, Jandro L. Abot, Issac M. Daniel. Processing of clay/epoxy nanocomposites by shear mixing. *Scripta Mater* 2003;49:81-6
- [4] Ke Wang, Ling Chen, Jingshen Wu, Mei Ling Toh, Chaobin He, Albert F. Yee. Epoxy nanocomposites with highly exfoliated clay: mechanical properties and fracture mechanism. *Macromolecules* 2005;38:788-800
- [5] Shao-Yun Fu, Xi-Qiao Feng, Bernd Lauke, Yiu-Wing Mai. Effects of particle size, particle/matrix interface adhesion and particle loading on mechanical properties of particulate-polymer composites. *Compos Part B: Eng* 2008;39:933-61
- [6] K.C. Yung, J. Wang, T.M. Yue. Modeling Young's modulus of polymer-layered silicate nanocomposites using a modified Halpin-Tsai micromechanical model. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics & Composites* 2006;25(8):847-61
- [7] N. Sheng, M.C. Boyce, D.M. Parks, G.C. Rutledge, J.I. Abes, R.E. Cohen. Multiscale micromechanical modeling of polymer/clay nanocomposites and the effective clay particle. *Polymer* 2004;45:487-506
- [8] Jyi-Jiin Luo, Isaac M. Daniel. Characterization and modeling of mechanical behavior of polymer/clay nanocomposites. *Compos Sci Technol* 2003;63:1607-16
- [9] D. Shia, C.Y. Hui. An Interface model for the prediction of Young's modulus of layered silicate-elastomer nanocomposites. *Polym Compos* 1998; 19(5):608-17
- [10] Chun-ki Lam, Hoi-yan Cheung, Kin-tak Lau, Li-min Zhou, Man-wai Ho, David Hui. Cluster size effect in hardness of nanoclay/epoxy composites. *Compos Part B: Eng* 2005;36:263-9
- [11] Chun-ki Lam, Kin-tak Lau, Hoi-yan Cheung, Hang-yin Ling. Effect of ultrasound sonication in nanoclay clusters of nanoclay/epoxy composites. *Mater Lett* 2005;59:1369-72
- [12] Man-wai Ho, Chun-ki Lam, Kin-tak Lau, Dickson H.L. Ng, David Hui. Mechanical properties of epoxy-based composites using nanoclays. *Compos Struct* 2006;75:415-21
- [13] Isil Isik, Ulku Yilmazer, Goknur Bayram. Impact modified epoxy/montmorillonite nanocomposites: synthesis and characterization. *Polymer* 2003;44:6371-7
- [14] Suprakas Sinha Ray, Masami Okamoto. Polymer/layered silicate nanocomposites: a review from preparation to processing. *Prog Polym Sci* 2003;28:1539-1641
- [15] Y. Ke, C. Long, Z. Qi. Preparation and properties of organo soluble montmorillonite/polyimide hybrid materials. *J Apply Polym Sci* 1999;73:2063-8
- [16] M. Song, D.J. Hourston, K.J. Yao, J.K.H. Tay, M.A. Ansarifard. High performance nanocomposites of polyurethane elastomer and organically modified layered silicate. *J Apply Polym Sci* 2003;90:3239-43